

This document contains the thematic model we synthesized based on interview materials in our study.

The thematic model is divided into two parts, namely **Practices** and **Challenges**, for identifying and using critical scenarios for testing autonomous driving systems in the industry. The thematic model is synthesized from right to left, meaning we start by analysing the code, then derive lower level themes, and gradually converge to the top (1st) level theme.

* To avoid repeatedly revisiting the original interviews in subsequent analysis, we keep the **Code** short but self-contained, meaning we incorporate necessary information, context, and some examples in the code to a minimum extent to index relevant segments we identified from the interview materials.

1st-level Theme	2nd-level Theme	3rd-level Theme	4th-level Theme	5th-level Theme	Code	Participant		
	Definition of Critical scenarios	Safety-relevant	Hazards		Scenarios that are safety-relevant and may cause potential hazards.	P12-13		
					Scenarios that have potential safety hazards and are uncommon, e.g., a vehicle approach to a pedestrian who's crossing when the traffic light is red.	P3		
				Risk of harm		Scenarios that could potentially harm a human being is considered critical, but the definition differs in different application domains.	P1	
						Scenarios that happen rarely and can harm the humans or AV.	P2	
						Potentially cause harm to objects or humans in the driving environment.	P9-10	
				Safety		Scenarios that are important for safety of the vehicle.	P11	
						Critical is a term from safety engineering and matters with how to clearly define the criticality with relevant criteria. A qualitative definition means you know what the criticality for the hazard is, what characteristics do they have and how to derive them from certain sources, and what is the casual relation between the hazard events and triggering conditions. A quantitative definition means you have a metric to evaluate the criticality, so either you use for example risk estimation based on probability and severity, or you invent other metrics to measure and represent the criticality.	P9-10	
						Critical scenarios are all scenarios that have safety concerns and are unsafe to proceed.	P5	
						We use edge cases instead of critical scenarios.	P9-10	
				Edge cases	Performance boundaries		Edge cases are searched to identify the system performance boundaries and improve the system, instead of just looking into unsafe scenarios where individual scenario may not indicate how could you improve the system.	P9-10
			Functional failures			Failure of sensor detection as critical scenarios.	P8	
			Long tail distribution			Scenarios on the long tail of the scenario distribution.	P11	
			All relevant			All relevant scenarios are critical when technology is immature.	P6-7	
						If you would know some scenarios are safe and the AV can handle, then you don't test them and you focus on the critical scenarios, but the problem is you don't know until you test them, so they are still critical before that, even if they are simple and common scenarios.	P2	
						If you don't fully understand how changes are related to the test scenarios, you still have to re-test them all to assure the AV can handle them.	P2	
					Safety and Necessity for testing		Critical scenarios can mean two different things: they are critical because they are relevant and need to be tested, or they are critical in terms of system performance, so you push the scenarios to the performance boundaries of known scenarios and find unknown ones which might be problematic for AV.	P2
			Responsibilities	Multiple roles		Initiatives of having other roles, e.g., developers, except testers to create test scenarios for system under test as they know better of the system.	P11	
				Test engineers			There are specific teams of test engineers look into the systems and test strategies to define which test to perform (SIL, HIL, vehicle test, integration test etc.), including critical scenarios.	P1
			Coverage vs critical scenarios		Not over focus on critical scenarios	Not over focus on critical scenarios because they can be those simple scenarios, or scenarios that happen very rarely, the point is we have to proof the safety of the AV for all scenarios that are relevant.	P2	
					Prioritize coverage	Improve coverage	Coverage of scenarios is essential in test and that will include exploring the critical scenarios in its ODD.	P2
						Known standards	Scenarios that fall into the standards, e.g., SOTIF, receive the major focus and assured to be covered. That does not necessary means scenarios outside the standards are not considered, but get less efforts.	P12-13
					Prioritize critical scenarios	Performance boundaries	Focus on worst-case scenarios and assume any scenarios below them would be safe, e.g., sensor detection range.	P8
					Coverage and critical scenarios is debatable		Focus on critical test scenarios or test scenario coverage is a debate over the completeness and the long-tail issue.	P9-10

Context of critical scenario selection	Stage-based approach	Early stage		In the early stage of development, it's unnecessary to focus too much on critical scenarios and they don't help too much as most common and basic scenarios might fail.	P9-10
				Evolving different stages is mostly experience-based. In early stage, there is no finalized architecture, data, full requirements, and the purpose is to build a conceptual model or prototype.	P9-10
		Middle stage		The middle stage entails some major components are functioning in the system, and the architecture, data and test pipeline are more stable. The system can handle some known scenarios for example.	P9-10
				In the middle stage, it's mostly to validate specific properties or features for the most recent development objectives, e.g., perception, thus critical scenarios are still not the focus.	P9-10
		Mature stage		The mature stage is when you have integrated the system and a full AV and tested your system on public roads like Tesla and Waymo do, and is time to polish the system and to test in some complex or extreme situations, e.g., sharp cut-in, extreme weather, or events like pedestrians' joywalk cross.	P9-10
				In mature stage, the system is more stable and can handle most common scenarios, thus efforts and resources can be put on critical scenarios.	P9-10
	Liability-based approach	Determination of stages	Experience-based	Deciding the stages for the project is very intuitive and is natural when you are involved in the project.	P9-10
		Liability of AV Suppliers	All relevant scenarios	Complete AV suppliers have to make sure they can handle every possible scenario, including not just the critical scenarios.	P5
				AV suppliers who build the entire vehicle and driving systems by themselves will have full responsibilities and liabilities of it.	P5
		Liability of AD Suppliers	Critical scenarios	AD function suppliers may focus on avoiding problematic scenarios rather than all possible scenarios.	P5
	Coverage and critical scenarios must complement			AD function supplier have limited responsibilities/liabilities.	P5
		Liability shift		Responsibility or liability will shift the focus of test scenarios.	P5
				Coverage and critical scenarios must be used complementary. Critical scenarios that lead to hazards or hit the performance limit are important for testing, but common and known scenarios still need to be considered.	P12-13
				Coverage and critical scenarios must be combined, so large efforts are put on identifying more unknown scenarios, especially the hazardous ones, but we also have a scenario set needs to be fulfilled for every software release, and the scenario set expands as more scenarios are identified.	P12-13
				For machine learning specifically, for example, perception, you start by aiming for a higher coverage of images, and then the critical scenarios (edge images) which are hard to interpret for the neural network.	P10
				We can't just rely on critical scenarios only, because we will miss a lot of problems that can exist in the world.	P12-13
	Combine all approaches			We can't just think of and test those critical scenarios, but also to cover the common and known scenarios as well.	P12-13
				Combine different approaches to define test scenarios, such as experts, data, standards like SOTIF, and analyse what is missed in each approach.	P8
				There are different approaches to find critical scenarios and all of them should be considered to some degree.	P12-13
				No silver bullets for scenario-based testing or other testing approaches. We have to look at them all for testing AV.	P11
				All three approaches are used to test (find insufficiencies and triggering conditions) different part of the AV.	P8
				Every approach has its own limitations and needs to be complemented by the others to show the completeness of testing.	P8
				No silver bullets, for example, for simulation testing, we work with fully synthetic data, partial synthetic data, and real-world data. None of them can stand on its own and need to be complemented by each other.	P11
				No silver bullets, for example, for critical scenario identification, expert approach gives a lot short-term wins, search-based may give you better coverage, but data-driven is always needed to look at realistic data.	P11
Combined			There are problems with either of the approaches: coverage with experts, cost with data-driven, and relevance of scenarios for search-based.	P11	
			Use data-driven and expert knowledge in the industry since you have more access to data and resources.	P1	

Critical scenario identification approaches	Data-driven	Examples/cases	AEB system	Define hazardous events and search in collected data for triggers of the events.	P8
			Public data and analysis	Data collection is not prioritized since we trust third-parties who provide different data and data analysis.	P6-7
			Fleet test data	Use perception fleet test data to find unknown insufficiencies and triggering conditions as well as acceptance level for sensors.	P8
				A big and representative data set, i.e., 300,000 km, is collected and used for testing AEB functionality.	P8
				Use simulation and ideal sensing data to test and search for functional insufficiencies.	P8
				Data approach is the basis for every system, they look into all statistics to define the system requirements, including for testing.	P12-13
			Online monitoring	One solution is to monitor the performance of system in production and collect data (near-misses, near-collisions) to identify new critical scenarios before real accidents happen, so that we can test those scenarios and improve the system to avoid them.	P1
				Running the AD system in shadowing mode so it gets the sensor data and calculates the decisions but do not control. It compares the decision with the operating software and evaluates how they differ, and detects more critical scenarios.	P2
				One approach is to deploy and test the shadowing functions, which means the system is deployed on the vehicle but not active in controlling the system. It gets the sensor inputs and reacts, but only in the background. It enables testing the system in real environment and identifies unknown hazardous scenarios that could potentially harm the driver for example.	P1
			Limitations	Understand data	One challenge with data-driven approach is how to detect critical scenarios from collected data.
	Data-driven approach is not used as much as it could. For example, we get a lot of consumer data, weather data, and others. We could use the data to detect some critical scenarios, for example, when a hard brake occurred.	P4			
	Costs	Challenge with data-driven approach, collect and annotate the data.		P11	
		Challenge with data-driven approach to remain relevant, there is huge cost associates with collect and label data especially when system evolves.		P11	
		Data-driven and search-based can go further after experts in detecting scenarios, but come with different costs.		P11	
	Quality of simulation	One problem with re-simulate scenarios from data is to ensure the extracted and simulated scenarios are still the same as real scenarios.		P11	
		One big challenge with data-driven approach for re-simulate from data is to maintain the fidelity of simulation for perception system.		P11	
		A problem with data-driven approach is to have a good visualization system to capture enough information from data and represent the scenarios as in the real-world context.		P11	
	Quality of data	Data-driven approach is subject to, for example, the sensor setup. So, if you change the sensor setup, you need to re-collect all data and scenarios.		P9-10	
		One problem with data-driven approaches is the representativeness and completeness of the data. For example, accident reports, and most accidents for human drivers (e.g., alcohol, distractions) do not apply for autonomous vehicles.		P2	
		Collect real traffic data is very important, but collecting data with host vehicle is different from infrastructure sensors, because with host vehicle the data is dependent on how the vehicle drives, but with infrastructure sensors you see different interactions from an independent lens.	P2		
Data-driven approach is also depending on how data is collected, for example, which sensors are used and how the sensors are installed. Having sensors on the vehicle or installed somewhere else is different.		P3			
Immense amount of data with variation is always needed to develop and test the systems, but you might not find all data from real-world.		P1			
Relevance of data	An accident for a human driver who speeding up to 200km/h and collide is not relevant for AV because AV is designed to follow the speed limit.	P2			
	On the contrary, there are many scenarios where human drivers avoided the accidents, e.g., mechanical failure or misbehavior of other road users, are relevant and critical for AV but are never reported.	P2			

Search-based	Examples/cases	Scenario creation	Creating critical images via either finding or synthesizing images that could be critical, for example, partially occluded images, or rotating images.	P9-10	
			Manipulate images to be artificially critical in order to make the neural network more robust.	P9-10	
			Not too much into search-based approach, and should invest more in it because more testing approaches are required.	P11	
		Performance boundaries	Critical scenarios and search-based approaches can help you explore the system performance boundary and generate more test scenarios.	P9-10	
		Efficiency	Search-based approach is not used but an efficient way of generating test scenarios in simulation	P1	
		System insufficiencies	Exploratory testing (search-based approach) is used from both collected data and simulated data, to identify insufficiencies of the system.	P12-13	
	Limitations	Hardware aspects	Hardware specifications, e.g., quality of sensors, are currently not included in critical scenario identification.	P6-7	
			If only this searching algorithms used, you might get a lot of failure or unsafe scenarios, which may not be very useful, so we need to combine it wisely.	P9-10	
			One problem with search-based approach is that we could identify critical scenarios that have very low probability of occurrence.	P6-7	
		Relevance of scenarios	Knowing what we are testing is important. For example, there might be very few scenarios related to perception out of a large number of tested scenarios that could be seem as unnecessary.	P11	
			Search-based approach can find critical scenarios that for example, crashes with high speed, but we need to understand the relevance of how likely they happen in real-world traffic, what are the occurrence rate. There could be scenarios that are severe but happen extremely rare then we wouldn't be able to list, test, and handle every scenario like that.	P2	
		Quality of simulation	A challenge with search-based approach is a good sensor simulation, otherwise it will be just optimizing the post-perception part.	P11	
	Initiatives	Include relevance of scenarios		One way is to not evaluate relevance of scenarios after but include it in the scenario generation. For example, set a residual risk for generated scenarios which is the probability to collide multiple by the occurrence rate.	P2
				There will always be some residual risks - some critical scenarios might happen but very rare, so we as in other fields, e.g., aerospace, to put an acceptance level to restrict the maximum risks to be tolerated.	P2
				Probability of occurrence should be considered in scenario identification process to generate more realistic scenarios.	P6-7
				Using real-world data as a source to analyse the probability or distribution of the generated critical scenarios.	P6-7
		Include realistic human behavior		Include human perspective, e.g., user behavior, in critical scenario identification.	P5
				Identify and test unknown scenarios (e.g., malicious behaviors from other road users, trust (mistrust) in AD (human perspective)).	P5
				Significance of human or human capability in driving and driving safety, and how can AD catch that while human is out of the loop.	P5
				Major cause of accidents in AV reported: misuse of AV by human.	P5
				Learning of driving and perceiving safety of the environment for human.	P5
				AV has to not only perceiving the environment, but also evaluating what and where is safe or unsafe.	P5
		Include hardware perspectives		Research in systematic selection of parameters for scenario parameterization is needed.	P5
				Include sensor perspective into scenario exploration to identify more realistic critical scenarios especially for the perception.	P11
Include architecture dependencies		Critical scenarios can also be identified from centralized computers (one computer for all systems for reducing costs) and dependencies among the different parts of the system, in a way that changing one part of the system may potentially affects other parts.	P3		
Use ODD specifications		Evaluate scenario relevance on ODD and function specifications.	P8		
		Inclusion and exclusion of test scenarios when it comes to which critical scenarios are relevant should be grounded on system ODD specification.	P6-7		
		The system ODD determines the scope of the test scenarios and limits the unknowns.	P4		

					Mathematically or logically validate whether generated scenarios are relevant, for example, using real-world data set to see the occurrence, despite a fact that we might generate a huge amount of scenarios from the parameter space.	P2	
	Validation and evaluation	Generated critical scenarios	Relevance	Use collected data	Analyse and evaluate generated scenarios with other scenarios already defined, for example, by experts, or extracted from data, to determine whether they are actually relevant or not.	P4	
					Having too many scenarios, even irrelevant scenarios, is not a big concern as we need more scenarios as potential candidates for test.	P4	
				Non-occurring is not necessarily irrelevant	Those rare (or even never happened) and complex scenarios can still be relevant for test, because we need to know how AV will react on that. Critical scenarios that have not happened can happen in the future.	P3	
					It's still the AV's responsibility, even if not to avoid, but to mitigate risks for those unknown scenarios, for example, via handover to safety drivers or stop the vehicle. The point is the AV, even without knowing such scenarios, still needs to be tested and understood how it will manage them.	P3	
	Tools and platforms	Simulation tools	Scenario execution		Using re-simulation tool to run recorded data for testing new software or changes of software.	P8	
		Game engine	Scenario creation		Simulation is not perfect and may not replicate the real environment faithfully, but it gives us a basis and approximation. If the vehicle does not work in simulation, there might be some issues.	P2	
		Limitations	Quality of simulation		One way to test the critical scenarios is to put the vehicle in the game server i.e., GTA, and create some challenging scenarios that involve evasive driving maneuvers from other road users.	P3	
	General initiatives	Develop fail-operational mechanisms	Fail-operational		Gaps exist between simulation testing and real-world testing, e.g., noises (e.g., weather and temperature might affect the sensors) are not added and how close the simulation is. Gap analysis is needed.	P3	
			Risk mitigation		Component degradation via fail-operational mechanism which allows the AV to indicate unknown scenarios and request intervention.	P5	
			Strategies for unknown		Unavoidable collisions are not the problem and can happen in real world as well, which we could only minimize the damage as much as possible.	P9-10	
					One way of mitigating the infinite number of possible scenarios is to cover knowns and assume fall-backs for unknowns.	P11	
					Not over focus on unknowns - finding all unknowns scenarios, but improving the system to not actively cause any accidents.	P11	
					Not over focus on unknowns and set reasonable expectations for AV - not avoiding all hazardous scenarios, but minimizing the risks by for example defensive driving for those scenarios.	P11	
					Example of covering knowns and assuming fall-backs for unknown, horse carriage on the public roads for Tesla, and assuming a defensive driving (e.g., slow-down or pull-over) for unknowns to not hit things.	P11	
			Set acceptance level for collisions		Set an acceptance rate for some collisions that are unavoidable, which could happen but we set a statistically acceptable level.	P12-13	
			Combine different approaches			Important to use various approaches for testing.	P6-7
						Combining experts and search-based approaches, so experts can analyse and evaluate as well as select whether generated critical scenarios from search-based approaches are relevant or not.	P11
					Expert knowledge and analysis has to be included when set up the searching process of critical scenarios for a certain function or system.	P9-10	
		Continuous monitoring			To use all resources available, including academic research results e.g., generated scenarios, as one source or inspiration at least.	P8	
		Continuous evolving			Continuously monitor and search for insufficiencies and potential hazards after releasing the AD function as well as fixing them.	P8	
		Continuous learning and improving			Critical scenarios have to grow and evolve as well, since new traffic infrastructures, entities (e.g., scooters), and behaviors exist.	P12-13	
					Critical scenario identification for testing is definitely the way to go because we can't think of everything and analyse the system beforehand, and the system will evolve as well. Instead, use continuous approach and iterate the testing with feedback, data, and known scenarios.	P3	
		Existing standards do not cover all critical scenarios			Standards and regulations do not define and cover all malicious scenarios (misuse or abuse are included in SOTIF, but not hijack, remote control).	P5	

Challenges	Insufficient definition of critical scenarios	Implementation-specific			Critical scenarios are OEM-specific due to the different implementation (e.g., strategies for avoiding hazardous) and sensors (e.g., Tesla is vision only) modalities or sensor hierarchy used.	P8		
					For perception module, which is ML-based, we don't really know how to define what are the critical scenarios.	P12-13		
		Criticality hard to define			Most problems are solved by exploring more unknown scenarios, you may focus on severe collisions after reaching to a low enough incident rate, but you don't just focus on the extreme cases and assume everything else would be handled. For perception, you can't say one scenario is more difficult than the others.	P12-13		
		Probability of occurrence	Probability			One challenge with the critical scenarios is to understand the likelihood of the occurrences of them.	P5	
						Understand the occurrence rate of a critical scenario generated.	P12-13	
			Distribution			Scenario frequency - how often the scenario happened in real-world traffic.	P5	
					A critical scenario may be included only after it occurred and being noticed, or otherwise it's not known beforehand and not tested.	P5		
	Coverage				It's impossible to predict all critical scenarios and the responsibilities still go to the fully autonomous vehicle if that happen.	P5		
					We need to identify and test unknown scenarios (e.g., accidents, falling objects such as flying tire) which are not in the test.	P5		
					Testing critical scenarios is mandatory, the problem is whether or how do we know that we have covered all unknown critical scenarios.	P5		
					We will never know whether we have covered all unknown scenarios in test, even for low-level AD functions.	P5		
					Unknown scenarios still exist and can happen in the traffic, and there are technical gaps in recognizing all these, but we identify and test those unknown scenarios (e.g., different animals) when they occur.	P5		
					Not knowing whether we covered all unknown scenarios or not.	P8		
	Completeness				Another challenge is that you cannot define and test unknown scenarios because they are unknown, so you can only test robustness of the system for any surprising inputs (unknown hazardous scenarios).	P1		
					Critical scenarios are not known in advance, we will analyse and handle those scenarios (failures, faulty scenarios) until they actually occur.	P6-7		
					The major limitation is that you don't know the unknown scenarios beforehand, those scenarios remain unknown until they happened.	P1		
			Realism	Physical constraints and ODD boundaries unclear			The generated scenarios are problematic or not realistic, because we do not strictly or precisely define the searching scope and targets, for example, limiting speed (maximum speed or relative speed) in a good way. Otherwise, the algorithm can search and find corresponding critical scenarios for SUT.	P9-10
							Unavoidable collisions do not mean they are unrealistic.	P9-10
							Unrealistic scenarios could mean, unrealistic behavior of the road users in the scenario, for example, the way how vehicle is performing cut-in, or the simulation is unrealistic, e.g., lidar simulation is unrealistic so it gives something which is not representing how the perception system could work with actual lidar in the production environment.	P11
						It is important to know all the constraints and boundaries of the ODD.	P12-13	
						To understand physical constraints and boundaries (certain speed, road curvature and inclination) and combination of them (some of them may depend on the others) of real traffic to improve realism of generated scenarios.	P12-13	
					Physical constraints that lead to impossible scenarios such as reaction time, break activation, tire friction, so some behaviors are impossible to perform and some situations are infeasible to avoid.	P12-13		
			Scenarios can be impossible in behavior of other vehicles or unavoidable by the host vehicle due to physical constraints.	P12-13				
			Search-based approach can generate unrealistic scenarios and a reference (interpretation of the scenarios) is needed to analyse the scenario.	P12-13				
		One challenge for critical scenario generation is the feasibility or realism of the generated critical scenarios.	P12-13					
Assessment criteria hard to define								

					Generate a critical scenario may not be too difficult, but understand the relevance of it is tricky, even for a simple scenario such as a vehicle behind cut in for a lane-keep function.	P2
		Relevance	Lack of understanding		Agreed in the industry with significance but no answer to what is the scenario catalog for testing and what are the critical scenarios. We need to collect a lot of data and systematically retrieve or generate those critical scenarios as well as understanding the occurrence rate.	P2
			AD and HD have different criticalities		Human driving collisions may not be relevant for autonomous vehicles as many accidents are due to human mistakes like distractions, we need to identify where to focus when it comes to simulate and test those scenarios.	P12-13
					Human driving may have different type of criticality and relevance for autonomous driving. Problems for human may not be problems for AV, and vice versa.	P12-13
					Major cause of accidents in AV reported: misuse of AV by human.	P5
	CSI approaches hard to implement	Expert intensive			Expert knowledge or prior data is needed to generate and validate critical scenarios, or otherwise it can be hard to know which scenarios are critical and how realistic they are, and how good the simulation is.	P1
					The limitation with critical scenario based testing is it heavily relies on expert knowledge. We collected a lot of data, e.g., accidents, but we still need experts to determine which data is more critical.	P1
		Ambiguous ODD specifications			ODD specification is insufficient (ambiguity of statements for nuanced parameter selection, e.g., how to quantify rain, snow)	P6-7
					The first challenge comes with the critical scenario based testing is to clearly define the ODD.	P1
					Selection of relevant parameters for scenario parameterization must be comprehensive and systematic which requires expertise and frameworks.	P5
		Incomplete ODD specifications			Critical scenario-based, or generally saying scenario-based testing, can only cover the parameters in the ODD specifications such as weather, road curvature, but many things that are not included in the ODD still need to be tested as well, e.g., fault injection.	P9-10
					An example is the occurrence of a system or component failure in the AV, which is not specified in the ODD and thus is not covered by scenario-based testing and SOTIF, but more on the functional safety in ISO-26262.	P9-10
		Coverage and completeness unknown			There are different work for identifying potential hazards of functional insufficiency and improvements to fix, but there is a risk of sub-optimizing the system if only focusing on that and may introduce new problems which were not problems before.	P12-13
					A general limitation is only scenarios within the ODD are considered and some unknown aspects would be missed when creating the scenarios.	P9-10
					Critical scenario-based testing is definitely needed, but the main challenge is how to make sure all critical scenarios are identified and tested.	P4
					We need to understand how much real data is needed to validate the relevance of scenarios and which distribution to use to sample scenarios for, because some distributions are very complex.	P2
		Data processing	Distribution and probability unknown		Scenario multiplication from the parameter space, but a distribution is needed to interpolate or extrapolate relevant scenarios, and deep learning can be used to learn from the collected driving data and the distribution of parameter to generate new scenarios.	P2
					Data is needed in search-based approaches to know how much a particular scenario could happen.	P2
			Quality and diversity unsure		The pre-requisite to use data-driven approach is that we need a big data set which covers diverse scenarios.	P2
		Lack of competences, technologies, and tools		The challenge comes with the data-driven approach is different competences are needed to work with the volume and complexity of the data, to understand, and extract different scenarios and corresponding indications from the data.	P4	
				The challenge is how to select data and criteria to use for identifying or extracting critical scenarios from.	P4	
		Hard to collect rare scenarios		An example of the data collection problems is machine learning needs a lot of samples but many samples (accidents) are so rare and can only be collected with immense driving mileage.	P1	
	Insufficient tools and platforms	Quality of simulation		The biggest challenge for scenario generation is to have a good simulation of the environment, so the sensor can give a good representation of the environment, currently is manually created and not scalable.	P11	